

LISTENING SKILLS AND STRATEGIES

Sabina Askarova

Al-Bukhari University, ESL/ESP teacher

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ANNOTATSIYA

During the communication it is vital that speakers understand each other, and this happens by listening. For a language learner it is a skill that should be acquired to improve their listening comprehension. The article discusses various listening skill, subskills and the strategies to improve those skills.

Difference between listening skills and strategies

Although being a receptive skill, listening is considered to be one of the most demanding skills for most learners. It requires adequate abilities to acquire the new language pieces. Those listening skills are the result of continuous learning practice. Since learners gain the necessary abilities in their listening process they will come up with, they will develop their listening strategies. These strategies are the planned and adopted way of listening that is useful to overcome listening challenges. According to Pearson and Paris (2008), listening skills should be improved into automatized listening skills with time. The only road to moving from listening skills to an effective strategy is time. Once learners are challenged with different discourses and within different levels and accents, the way between skills and strategies becomes far easier. From my experience, I would say there is no super powerful way to improve listening skills

without giving yourself a couple of periods to get accustomed to various speeches, tones, and speed rates, and then, the improvement can be seen as you select your strategy. As for me, metacognitive strategies worked best as it consists of planning, monitoring, and evaluation which is essential to achieving the target goal. Thus, these two aspects are correlated and arduous at times but can be achieved if you can select the suitable strategy that works for you or you may just use the blending of strategy according to the purpose of your listening tasks.

Comparison of the listening subskills

Regarding J.C. Richards (1983)'s taxonomy and its correspondence with Vandegrift and Goh (2012), it is obvious that there are matchable features between them. One salient example of this can be the parallelism of selectiveness in listening core skills and the ability to pick up lexical items on a certain topic. Students should listen to specific parts of the lecture and skip other unnecessary information. In

addition, another matching can be listening for global understanding which is a core skill in the listening process, and the student's ability to grasp the aim and scope of the lecture in Richard's academic subskills taxonomy. Taking advantage of both, learners become the more competent listener. This detailed list of subskills and core categories is very handy for the teachers because they play a role of a guideline for teaching listening. Therefore, instructors should shape their students by giving various tasks that can develop each subskill of their students' listening comprehension to reach professional listeners.

Academic listening vs. General listening

There are considerable differences when it comes to academic listening and other types, mostly general listening. Academic listening is frequently associated with

academic lecture comprehension, seminars, projects, or academic group discussions. Students need to develop academic language skills such as the use of terms and complex sentence structures. Other listening types tend to be more colloquial and daily life contexts that are effortless to understand and acquire the meaning. Listening to music, watching movies, and listening to the radio can be full of various conversations and common, widespread media, which are used mostly for pleasure.

In a nutshell, listening skills are key demanded abilities to develop listening strategies that can lead to a definite listening proficiency. Communication can be possible if strict practice and implementation of core skills and strategies from both sides, namely teachers and learners.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Christine C.M. Goh (2014), Second language Listening comprehension: Process and Pedagogy
2. John Flowerdew & Lindsay Miller(2014), Dimensions of Academic listening
3. J.C. Richards (1983), Listening comprehension: Approach, Design, Procedure
4. Vandergrift, L. & Goh, Ch. (2012). Teaching and Learning Second Language Listening: Metacognition in Action
5. <https://www.britishcouncil.org/voices-magazine/prepare-english-language-students-academic-listening>